

Kinetics and mechanism of oxidation of iron(II) by *N*-chloro-*p*-substituted-benzenesulfonamides

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The kinetics of oxidation of Fe^{II} by *N*-chloro-*N*-sodiobenzenesulfonamide (chloramine-B, CAB), *N*-chloro-*N*-sodio-*p*-methylbenzenesulfonamide (chloramine-T, CAT or CABB), *N*-chloro-*N*-sodio-*p*-ethylbenzenesulfonamide (CAEB), *N*-chloro-*N*-sodio-*p*-chlorobenzenesulfonamide (CACB), *N*-chloro-*N*-sodio-*p*-bromobenzenesulfonamide (CABB) and *N*-chloro-*N*-sodio-*p*-iodobenzenesulfonamide (CAIB) in aqueous sulfuric acid medium have been investigated. The observed kinetics of first order in [oxidant], fractional order each in [Fe^{II}] and [SO₄²⁻], and inverse fractional order in [H⁺] have been explained by a mechanism involving the formation of an intermediate by the direct interaction between the oxidising species ArSO₂NH₂Cl⁺ and [Fe^{II}], which subsequently undergoes disproportionation in the rate-determining step leading to Fe^{III}, respective sulfonamide and Cl⁻. The related rate law has been deduced. The activation parameters have also been computed. The constancy of the free energies of activation may signal the operation of similar mechanism in all the cases.

The oxidative strength of the *N*-chloro-*N*-sodio-benzenesulfonamides depends on the ease with which Cl⁺ is released from the reagent, as Cl⁺ is the effective oxidising species in the reactions of *N*-chloroamides. The ease with which Cl⁺ is released from the *N*-chloroamide depends on the quantum of electron density on the nitrogen atom of the

amide group. This in turn depends on the nature of the substituent in the benzene ring as electron-donating groups increase the electron density on the nitrogen atom, while the electron-withdrawing groups lower it. Hence it is expected that with electron-withdrawing groups in the benzene ring, Cl⁺ is released much more easily than with the electron-

Table 1. Pseudo-first order rate constants (k_{obs}) for the oxidation of Fe^{II} by *N*-chloro-*p*-substituted-benzenesulfonamides

$I = 0.60 \text{ mol dm}^{-3}$, Temp. = 303 K									
$10^4 [\text{oxidant}]_0$	$10^2 [\text{Fe}^{\text{II}}]_0$	$10^2 [\text{H}_2\text{SO}_4]$	$10^3 [\text{H}^+]_{\text{eff}}$	$10^4 k_{\text{obs}} (\text{s}^{-1})$					
mol dm ⁻³	mol dm ⁻³	mol dm ⁻³	mol dm ⁻³	CAB	CAMB	CAEB	CACB	CABB	CAIB
Effect of varying [oxidant] ₀ :									
2.0	2.0	1.0	3.4	28.4	19.5	19.5	49.5	48.4	34.4
3.0	2.0	1.0	3.4	26.5	19.9	19.3	47.7	47.2	33.2
5.0	2.0	1.0	3.4	26.8	20.2	19.0	44.6	45.6	33.2
10.0	2.0	1.0	3.4	27.0	19.8	19.9	44.2	42.2	33.6
20.0	2.0	1.0	3.4	27.0	19.8	19.1	43.5	40.6	29.8
Effect of varying [Fe ^{II}] ₀ :									
5.0	0.5	1.0	3.4	8.4	6.4	6.1	11.4	16.9	9.6
5.0	1.0	1.0	3.4	14.6	11.7	10.7	24.6	25.6	17.3
5.0	2.0	1.0	3.4	26.8	20.2	19.6	44.6	45.6	33.2
5.0	3.0	1.0	3.4	37.0	29.2	25.6	62.2	64.8	47.7
5.0	5.0	1.0	3.4	58.0	40.3	36.8	95.8	111.3	73.5
Effect of varying [H ₂ SO ₄] ₀ :									
5.0	2.0	0.3	1.0	87.3	53.7	42.0	73.4	78.5	85.9
5.0	2.0	0.5	1.3	50.5	36.7	33.5	63.9	65.1	75.5
5.0	2.0	1.0	3.4	26.8	20.4	19.3	44.7	45.6	33.2
5.0	2.0	2.0	7.4	12.9	10.8	10.3	28.9	30.0	31.3
5.0	2.0	3.0	11.2	8.0	7.1	7.1	21.1	23.9	24.4
5.0	2.0	5.0	25.0	4.7	4.6	4.3	11.1	19.6	14.5
5.0	2.0	10.0	68.0	1.5	1.3	0.9	2.3	3.9	6.0

donating groups in the benzene ring of substituted *N*-chloro-*N*-sodiobenzenesulfonamides. Thus it is possible to produce an oxidant of desired strength by introducing an appropriate group in the benzene ring of the *N*-chloroarylamide. As a part of our efforts in the direction of introducing oxidants or reagents of varying strength, we have prepared several substituted *N*-chloro-*N*-sodiobenzenesulfonamides and employed them for studying the kinetics of oxidation of Fe^{II} in aqueous medium. We report herein the kinetics of oxidation of Fe^{II} by *N*-chloro-*N*-sodio-*p*-methylbenzenesulfonamide (chloramine-T, CAT or CAMB), *N*-chloro-*N*-sodio-*p*-ethylbenzenesulfonamide (CAEB), *N*-chloro-*N*-sodio-*p*-chlorobenzenesulfonamide (CACB), *N*-chloro-*N*-sodio-*p*-bromobenzenesulfonamide (CABB) and *N*-chloro-*N*-sodio-*p*-iodobenzenesulfonamide (CAIB) and correlate the results.

There are very few reports on the mechanistic aspects of Fe^{II} oxidation¹. The kinetics of oxidation of Fe^{II} by *N*-halo, *N*-metallo and *N,N*-dihalo aromatic sulfonamides in water-methanol medium (1 : 1, v/v) have also been studied in the presence of sulphuric acid².

Results and Discussion

The kinetic data on the oxidation of Fe^{II} by CAB, CAMB, CAEB, CACB, CABB and CAIB in aqueous sulfuric acid (0.002–0.10 mol dm⁻³) under varying [oxidant], [Fe^{II}], [H⁺], [SO₄²⁻] and temperature are shown in Tables 1-3.

Table 2. Pseudo-first order rate constants (k_{obs}) as [SO₄²⁻] is varied for the oxidation of Fe^{II} by *N*-chloro-*p*-substituted-benzenesulfonamides in aqueous sulfuric acid at 303 K

10 ² [SO ₄ ²⁻] (I) mol dm ⁻³	10 ⁴ k_{obs} (s ⁻¹)					
	CAB	CAMB	CAEB	CACB	CABB	CAIB
9.4 (0.3)	19.8	12.5	13.3	35.1	34.8	26.1
19.4 (0.6)	26.8	20.9	19.2	44.7	45.6	33.3
33.6 (1.0)	37.5	28.3	26.3	52.9	56.6	41.3
49.4 (1.5)	48.4	41.0	31.7	64.6	65.6	50.6

Table 3 Kinetic data for the oxidation of Fe^{II} by *N*-chloro-*p*-substituted-benzenesulfonamides in aqueous sulfuric acid media

Orders in	CAB	CAMB	CAEB	CACB	CABB	CAIB
[Oxidant]	1.0	1.0	1.0	1.0	1.0	1.0
[Fe ^{II}]	0.8	0.9	0.8	0.8	0.9	0.9
[H ₂ SO ₄]	1.0	0.9	0.6	0.7	0.6	0.6
[H ⁺] _{eff}	1.0	0.9	0.7	0.6	0.6	0.6
[SO ₄ ²⁻]	0.5	0.6	0.5	0.4	0.4	0.4

Effect of varying [oxidant]₀: At constant [Fe^{II}]₀ (5–50 fold excess over [oxidant]₀), [H⁺] and [SO₄²⁻], the first order plots of log [oxidant] versus time were linear up to at least 75% completion of the reactions. The pseudo-first order rate constants computed from the plots remained unaffected by the changes in [oxidant]₀ (Table 1), establishing first order dependence of the rate on [oxidant], in all the cases.

At constant [oxidant]₀, [H⁺] and [SO₄²⁻], the rates increased with increase in [Fe^{II}] with fractional order dependences in [Fe^{II}] for all the oxidations (Table 1). The plots of k_{obs} versus [Fe^{II}] were non-linear, while the double-reciprocal plots of $1/k_{obs}$ versus $1/[Fe^{II}]$ were linear with finite intercepts on the ordinates, indicating the operation of Michaelis-Menten type mechanism for the oxidation of Fe^{II} by all the oxidants. The rates decreased with increase in [H⁺], at fixed [oxidant]₀ and [Fe^{II}]₀, with inverse fractional order kinetics in [H⁺] with all the oxidants (Table 1). The plots of $1/k_{obs}$ versus [H₂SO₄] or [H⁺]_{eff} were linear. The rates increased with increase in [SO₄²⁻], at fixed [oxidant]₀, [Fe^{II}]₀ and [H⁺], with fractional order dependences in [SO₄²⁻] for the oxidation of Fe^{II} by all the oxidants (Table 2). The plot of $1/k_{obs}$ versus $1/[SO_4^{2-}]^{1/2}$ was linear in all the cases. It was further observed that the rates increased with increase in ionic strength of the medium (Table 2). The rates were measured at different temperatures and the activation parameters computed from the Arrhenius and Eyring plots.

Mechanism of oxidation :

The probable reactive form of the oxidants under the present aqueous acid conditions³⁻⁵ is likely to be ArSO₂NH₂Cl⁺. Hence the observed kinetics of first order in [oxidant], fractional order each in [Fe^{II}] and [SO₄²⁻], and inverse fractional order in [H⁺] may be explained by a mechanism involving the formation of an intermediate by the direct interaction between ArSO₂NH₂Cl⁺ and [Fe^{II}], which subsequently undergoes disproportionation in the rate-determining step leading to Fe^{III}, respective sulfonamide and Cl⁻,

Scheme 1

Applying the steady state approximation to the formation of X, we have

$$[\text{X}] = \frac{K_1 [\text{ArSO}_2\text{NH}_2\text{Cl}^+]_0 [\text{Fe}^{II}]}{[\text{H}^+] + K_1 [\text{Fe}^{II}]} \quad (1)$$

where $[\text{ArSO}_2\text{NH}_2\text{Cl}^+] = [\text{ArSO}_2\text{NH}_2\text{Cl}^+]_0 - [\text{X}]$ and $[\text{Fe}^{II}]_0 - [\text{X}] \cong [\text{Fe}^{II}]$.

The rate of reaction is given by

$$-\frac{d[\text{ArSO}_2\text{NH}_2\text{Cl}^+]}{dt} = k_2 [\text{X}] \quad (2)$$

Substituting for [X], we have

$$-\frac{d[\text{ArSO}_2\text{NH}_2\text{Cl}^+]}{dt} = \frac{K_1 k_2 [\text{ArSO}_2\text{NH}_2\text{Cl}^+]_0 [\text{Fe}^{II}]}{[\text{H}^+] + K_1 [\text{Fe}^{II}]} \quad (3)$$

Eqn. (3) may be rearranged as

$$-\frac{1}{[\text{ArSO}_2\text{NH}_2\text{Cl}^+]_0} \frac{d[\text{ArSO}_2\text{NH}_2\text{Cl}^+]}{dt} = \frac{K_1 k_2 [\text{Fe}^{\text{II}}]}{[\text{H}^+] + K_1 [\text{Fe}^{\text{II}}]} \quad (4)$$

But the left-hand side of eqn. (4) may be written as

$$-\frac{1}{[\text{ArSO}_2\text{NH}_2\text{Cl}^+]_0} \frac{d[\text{ArSO}_2\text{NH}_2\text{Cl}^+]}{dt} \approx \frac{-d \ln[\text{ArSO}_2\text{NH}_2\text{Cl}]}{dt} = k_{\text{obs}}$$

Eqn. (4) therefore takes the form,

$$k_{\text{obs}} = \frac{K_1 k_2 [\text{Fe}^{\text{II}}]}{[\text{H}^+] + K_1 [\text{Fe}^{\text{II}}]} \quad (5)$$

which may be further written as

$$\text{or } \frac{1}{k_{\text{obs}}} = \frac{[\text{H}^+]}{K_1 k_2} \frac{1}{[\text{Fe}^{\text{II}}]} + \frac{1}{k_2} \quad (6)$$

The plots of $1/k_{\text{obs}}$ versus $1/[\text{Fe}^{\text{II}}]$ and $1/k_{\text{obs}}$ versus $[\text{H}^+]$ or $[\text{H}_2\text{SO}_4]$ were linear for the oxidation of Fe^{II} by all the oxidants, in accordance with the rate law (6). The constants K_1 and k_2 were calculated from the slopes and intercepts of either of the plots for all the oxidations (Table 4). The constants calculated from $1/k_{\text{obs}}$ versus $1/[\text{Fe}^{\text{II}}]$ plots were used

Table 4. The coefficients of the rate-limiting steps, k_2 and the equilibrium constant, K_1 at different temperatures for the oxidation of Fe^{II} by *N*-chloro-*p*-substituted-benzenesulfonamides

Temp. K	CAB	CAMB	CAEB	CACB	CABB	CAIB
			$10^3 k_2 (\text{s}^{-1})$			
288	1.25 ^a	0.29 ^a	—	20.9	5.44	3.61
293	2.72	0.83	1.70	42.8	17.1	4.03
298	7.91	1.91	4.38	91.2	38.0	7.77
303	11.50	5.75	7.14	190.2	88.1	25.5
308	—	—	14.70	—	—	—
			$10^2 K_1$			
288	26.4 ^a	34.3 ^a	—	2.35	13.9	21.4
293	22.2	32.9	29.7	2.11	7.0	21.2
298	14.3	29.7	16.7	1.62	5.6	17.8
303	13.5	16.9	15.1	1.09	3.2	9.8
308	—	—	12.6	—	—	—

^aExtrapolated value.

to recalculate the rate constants from the rate law (5) as $[\text{H}_2\text{SO}_4]$ or $[\text{H}^+]_{\text{eff}}$ was varied (Table 5). Similar recalculations were made based on the constants calculated from the plots of either $1/k_{\text{obs}}$ versus $[\text{H}_2\text{SO}_4]$ or $1/k_{\text{obs}}$ versus $[\text{H}^+]_{\text{eff}}$ (Table 6). Reasonably good agreement between the recalculated rate constants and the experimental values tests the consistency of the rate law (5) and hence the validity of the suggested mechanism to explain the experimental observations.

Further, $[\text{Fe}^{\text{II}}]$ was varied at different temperatures (288, 293, 298, 303 and 308 K) with all the oxidants and the constants k_2 and K_1 were calculated at each temperature, with all the oxidants (Table 4). The activation parameters were also computed from the plots of $\log k_2$ versus $1/T$ and $\log(k_2/T)$ versus $1/T$ (Table 7).

Introduction of sulfuric acid dissociation equilibrium into the rate law (6),

gives the rate law (8),

$$\frac{1}{k_{\text{obs}}} = \frac{K_a^{1/2} [\text{H}_2\text{SO}_4]^{1/2}}{K_1 k_2 [\text{SO}_4^{2-}]^{1/2}} \frac{1}{[\text{Fe}^{\text{II}}]} + \frac{1}{k_2} \quad (8)$$

The plot of $1/k_{\text{obs}}$ versus $1/[\text{SO}_4^{2-}]^{1/2}$ was linear with all the oxidants in conformity with the rate law. Further, ionic strength plots were also linear.

Effective oxidising species of the oxidants employed in the present oxidations is Cl^+ in different forms. The introduction of different substituent groups in the benzene ring of the oxidant affects the ability of the reagent to oxidise the substrate. Therefore, it is expected that the electron-releasing groups such as CH_3 , C_2H_5 etc. inhibit the ease with which Cl^+ is released from the oxidant, while electron-withdrawing groups such as Cl , Br etc. enhance this ability. The present observations are in conformity with these trends. The decrease in rate of oxidation in going from CACB to CABB and CABB to CAIB may be due to the steric hindrances. Nevertheless the rates with both CABB and CAIB are greater than that with CAB.

Both the plots of $\log k_2$ versus σ_p and $\log k_{\text{obs}}$ versus σ_p were reasonably linear. The plot of ΔH^\ddagger versus ΔS^\ddagger was also linear with an isokinetic temperature of 296 K. Further to see the effect of substituent in the benzene ring of the oxidant on the energy of activation, E_a values of substituted oxidants were optimised corresponding to the $\log A$ value of CAB through the equation, $E_a = 2.303 RT (\log A - \log k_2)$. As may be seen (Table 7), the energies of activation for the oxidants with electron-releasing groups in the benzene ring are higher than that of the parent oxidant, CAB, while they are lower for the oxidants with the electron-withdrawing groups in the benzene ring. Enthalpies of activations have the same trend. Similarly, $\log A$ values were optimised corresponding to the E_a of CAB oxidation of Fe^{II} through the equation, $\log A = \log k_2 + E_a/2.303 RT$ (Table 7). As can be seen, $\log A$ values are higher for oxidants with the electron-withdrawing groups in the benzene ring and lower for those with the electron-releasing groups. The free energies of activation remain the same in both the optimisations.

Note

Table 5 Comparison between the recalculated rate constants from the rate law as $[H_2SO_4]$ and $[H^+]_{eff}$ are varied and the experimental values for the oxidation of Fe^{II} by *N*-chloro-*p* substituted-benzenesulfonamides at 303 K

$10^2 [H_2SO_4]$ mol dm ⁻³	$10^4 k (s^{-1})$									
	CAB		CAMB		CAEB		CACB		CABB	
	Recalc	Expt	Recalc	Expt	Recalc	Expt	Recalc	Expt	Recalc	Expt
0.5	48.3	50.5	34.3	36.7	32.8	33.5	80.0	63.9	86.1	65.1
1.0	26.8	26.8	20.7	20.9	19.5	19.1	45.2	44.7	46.1	45.6
2.0	14.1	12.9	11.5	10.8	10.8	10.3	26.6	28.9	24.7	30.0
3.0	9.6	8.0	8.0	7.1	7.5	7.1	18.5	21.1	16.7	23.9
5.0	5.8	4.7	4.9	4.6	4.6	4.3	11.4	11.1	10.2	19.6
10.0	2.9	1.5	2.5	1.3	2.4	0.9	5.8	2.3	5.1	3.9
$10^3 [H^+]_{eff}$										
1.3	60.0	50.5	41.0	36.7	39.3	33.5	79.4	63.9	88.2	65.1
3.4	27.0	26.8	21.0	20.9	20.2	19.1	40.4	44.7	47.4	45.6
7.4	13.0	12.9	11.0	10.8	10.1	10.3	28.3	28.9	28.5	30.0
11.2	8.8	8.0	7.4	7.1	6.9	7.1	14.8	21.1	15.6	23.9
25.0	4.0	4.7	3.4	4.6	3.2	4.3	6.6	11.1	7.3	19.6
68.0	1.0	1.5	1.3	1.3	1.2	0.9	2.5	2.3	2.6	3.9

Table 6 Comparison between the recalculated rate constants from the rate law as $[Fe^{II}]$ is varied and the experimental values for the oxidation of Fe^{II} by *N*-chloro-*p* substituted-benzenesulfonamides at 303 K

$10^2 [Fe^{II}]_0$ mol dm ⁻³	$10^4 k (s^{-1})$									
	CAB		CAMB		CAEB		CACB		CABB	
	Recalc	Expt	Recalc	Expt	Recalc	Expt	Recalc	Expt	Recalc	Expt
Recalculated values based on $[H_2SO_4]$ plots										
0.5	6.2	8.4	5.5	6.4	5.5	6.1	16.4	11.4	18.3	16.9
1.0	12.3	14.6	10.6	11.7	10.3	10.7	28.7	24.6	31.3	25.6
2.0	24.8	26.8	20.2	20.2	18.9	19.6	45.6	44.6	48.2	45.6
3.0	35.3	37.0	28.8	29.2	26.2	25.6	56.7	62.2	58.8	64.8
5.0	56.1	58.0	43.0	40.3	37.6	36.8	70.5	95.8	71.4	88.3
Recalculated values based on $[H^+]_{eff}$ plots										
0.5	8.0	8.4	6.5	6.4	6.6	6.1	18.7	11.4	21.4	16.9
1.0	14.8	14.6	11.9	11.7	11.8	10.7	30.8	24.6	34.7	25.6
2.0	26.2	26.8	20.6	20.2	19.5	19.6	45.5	44.6	50.2	45.6
3.0	35.2	37.0	27.3	29.2	24.9	25.6	54.1	62.2	59.0	65.8
5.0	48.4	58.0	36.8	40.3	31.9	36.8	63.7	95.8	68.6	88.3

Table 7 Activation parameters for the oxidation of Fe^{II} by *N*-chloro-*p*-substituted-benzenesulfonamides in aqueous sulfuric acid media

Parameter	CAB	CAMB	CAEB	CACB	CABB	CAIB
E_a (kJ mol ⁻¹)	114.0	133.5	104.7	111.4	106.2	113.2
log <i>A</i>	15.2	18.1	13.4	15.9	14.5	15.3
ΔH^\ddagger (kJ mol ⁻¹)	111.3	140.7	102.1	110.9	103.8	120.3
ΔS^\ddagger (J K ⁻¹ mol ⁻¹)	86.2	176.1	51.2	107.4	73.6	118.9
ΔG^\ddagger (kJ mol ⁻¹)	85.2	87.4	86.6	78.3	82.6	84.2
Optimised values corresponding to log <i>A</i> value of CAB						
E_a (kJ mol ⁻¹)	114.0	101.4	100.8	92.5	94.4	97.6
ΔH^\ddagger (kJ mol ⁻¹)	111.5	98.8	98.3	90.0	92.0	95.1
ΔG^\ddagger (kJ mol ⁻¹)	99.1	87.2	86.7	78.4	80.3	83.5
Optimised values corresponding to E_a value of CAB						
log <i>A</i>	15.2	17.4	17.5	18.9	18.6	18.1
ΔS^\ddagger (J K ⁻¹ mol ⁻¹)	37.6	79.8	81.7	108.9	102.6	92.2
ΔG^\ddagger (kJ mol ⁻¹)	99.9	87.1	86.6	78.3	80.2	83.4

Experimental

Analytical grade chloramine-T (Fluka, A.G.) was employed. Chloramine-B (CAB) was prepared by the partial chlorination of benzenesulfonamide⁵. The *N*-chloro-*p*-substituted-benzenesulfonamides were prepared by the reported method⁶ and characterised by m.p. and IR spectral data.

***N*-Chlorination** : Pure chlorine gas was bubbled through solutions of *p*-substituted-benzenesulfonamides in 4 *N* NaOH for 1 h at 70°. the precipitated *N*-chloro-*p*-substitutedbenzenesulphonamides were washed, dried and crystallised from water, and characterised by m.p. and IR spectral data. Aqueous stock solutions (0.05 mol dm⁻³) of the *N*-chloroarylsulfonamides were prepared in double-distilled water and stored in amber coloured bottles and standardised by the iodometric method. Ferrous ammonium sulfate (G.R., Merck) was used as the source of Fe^{II}. A stock solution (0.20 mol dm⁻³) of the compound in 0.02 mol dm⁻³ H₂SO₄ was prepared. Ionic strength of the medium was maintained at 0.60 mol dm⁻³ by employing concentrated aqueous solution of sodium sulfate. All other reagents used were of accepted grades of purity.

Kinetic measurements : The kinetic runs were made in glass stoppered pyrex boiling tubes under pseudo-first order conditions with [substrate] >> [oxidant] (5 to 50 times). The reactions were initiated by the rapid addition of requisite amounts of oxidant solution, pre-equilibrated at a desired temperature, to solution mixtures containing known amounts of ferrous ammonium sulfate (0.005–0.05 mol dm⁻³), sulfuric acid (0.002–0.10 mol dm⁻³), sodium sulfate and water, thermostated at the same temperature. The progress of the reactions was monitored for two half-lives by the iodometric estimation of the unreacted oxidant at regular intervals of time. The pseudo-first order rate constants were computed by the graphical methods and the values were reproducible within ±3% error.

Stoichiometry and product analysis : The stoichiometry of Fe^{II} *N*-chloroarylsulfonamide reactions was determined

by equilibrating varying ratios of [*N*-chloroarylsulfonamide] to [Fe^{II}] at 303 K and varying [H₂SO₄] (0.002–0.10 mol dm³). The presence of Fe^{II} in the reaction products was identified by colour reactions with acidified ammonium thiocyanate solution. The reduced products, *p*-substituted-benzenesulfonamides and benzenesulfonamide were detected by paper chromatography and TLC⁷, respectively. The presence of Fe^{III} in the reaction products was identified by colour reactions with acidified ammonium thiocyanate solution⁸. The observed stoichiometry may be represented as

where, Ar = *p*-X-C₆H₄ and X = -H, CH₃, C₂H₅, Cl, Br or I.

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